

Antimicrobial Potentiality of a New Beta Lactam Antibiotic Fosfomycin among Multidrug Resistant, Extended Spectrum Beta Lactamase Producing, Carbapenem Resistant Uropathogens

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Abstract:

Background: Urinary Tract Infections (UTIs) caused by Multidrug-Resistant (MDR) gram-negative bacteria, specifically Enterobacteriaceae, are a growing concern because of limited therapeutic options. Fosfomycin as a novel oral therapeutic option against the MDR uropathogens has been widely discussed recently.

Objectives: To know the local antimicrobial susceptibilities and to evaluate the activity of Fosfomycin against Extended-Spectrum Beta-Lactamase (ESBL) producing, Carbapenem-Resistant (CR) and MDR Uropathogens in Southern India.

Materials and Methods: A cross-sectional study was conducted in the Department of Microbiology of a tertiary care hospital from April to September 2023. Pathogenic organisms were identified from urine samples by conventional biochemical tests. Antibiotic sensitivity testing and ESBL production was tested for urinary isolates. Minimum Inhibitory Concentration (MIC) for Fosfomycin was determined by E-test. Data were analysed using Microsoft Excel 2016. Frequencies and percentages were determined for categorical variables.

Results: Out of the 58 positive isolates yielded after the urine culture, 36(68.6%) were E. coli, 16(10.16%) were Klebsiella spp., 4(6.77%) were Pseudomonas spp., 2(4.23%) were Proteus spp. Among 54 Enterobacteriaceae isolates, 41(75.93%) were ESBL producers, of which 31 were E. coli and 10 were K.pneumoniae. Among 54 Enterobacteriaceae isolates, 20(37.03%) were Carbapenem resistant Enterobacteriaceae and 19 (35.18%) isolates were found to be MDRE. However, all the isolates were found to be Fosfomycin susceptible both by disc diffusion method and by E-strips.

Conclusion: Fosfomycin might be a promising antibiotic for the treatment of uncomplicated UTIs due to E. coli. It has also shown good activity against ESBL-producing, CR, and MDR uropathogens.

Keywords: Urinary Tract Infections, Fosfomycin, Enterobacteriaceae, Carbapenem-Resistant, Extended Spectrum Beta Lactamase.

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Introduction

Urinary tract infection (UTI) is one of the most common clinical entities encountered by the medical practitioners. The most common organisms causing UTI are all known to harbour multiple drug resistance(MDR) mechanisms, both inherited or transmissible and chromosomal or extra chromosomal against the commonly used oral antimicrobial agents for UTI caused by Gram negative organisms, i.e., Fluoroquinolones, Trimethoprim- sulfamethoxazole, Nitrofurantoin and second and Third generation cephalosporins[1]. With rampant overuse and abuse of these drugs, particularly in the developing countries like India with availability of over the counter drugs, Gram-negative organisms have become overwhelmingly resistant to all or most of these agents, making outpatient oral therapy increasingly difficult. Extended spectrum Beta Lactamase (ESBL)

production is common among clinical isolates of Enterobacteriaceae. Since Carbapenems are considered drug of choice for serious infections caused by these microorganisms, use of these drugs is increasing, which is contributing to the selection and spread of Carbapenem-resistant Gram-negative bacilli [2]. Fosfomycin is an oral antibiotic with bactericidal activity against these MDR pathogens. It inhibits synthesis of the bacterial cell wall. It is best absorbed if given before food intake and is excreted in urine. It achieves high concentration in urine of 2000 µg/ml and maintains high levels for over 24 hrs. Hence, single time oral therapy with Fosfomycin has been recommended in uncomplicated UTI [3-6]. Existing literature suggests the use of Fosfomycin for the treatment of UTIs due to ESBL-producing, Carbapenem Resistant and MDR strains of Uropathogens.

However, data regarding in vitro susceptibility of Fosfomycin against ESBL producing, Carbapenem Resistant and MDR strains is lacking in the area where the current study will be conducted. Hence the present study was undertaken to determine in-vitro susceptibility of Fosfomycin.

Objectives

1. To find out the resistance pattern of common Uropathogens against commonly prescribed antimicrobial agents.
2. To determine in vitro Fosfomycin susceptibility against ESBL-producing, Carbapenem resistant and MDR strains of Uropathogens.

Materials and Methods

Study type: Cross sectional study

Study Centre: Department of Microbiology, Government Theni Medical College.

Study period: 6 months (April 2023 to September 2023)

Sample size: 100

Sample collection and processing

Ethical clearance was obtained from the Institutional ethical committee before the commencement of the study. Midstream specimens of urine were processed in the microbiology laboratory. Collected urine samples were inoculated onto Blood agar and MacConkey agar media by calibrated loop technique [7]. After overnight incubation, the samples which showed positive growth of organisms were processed. Organisms were identified by their colony morphology, staining characteristics, haemoly-

sis, motility and other relevant biochemical tests as per standard bacteriological methods [8].

Antibiotic sensitivity testing

Antibiogram for all the bacterial isolates was performed on Mueller-Hinton agar plates by Kirby-Bauer disc diffusion method and interpreted according to the Clinical and Laboratory Standards Institute (CLSI) guidelines M100-S26 version published in 2016 [9]. Antimicrobial discs used were Amikacin (30 µg), Gentamicin (10 µg), Nalidixic acid (30 µg), Nitrofurantoin (300 µg), Trimethoprim-sulfamethoxazole (1.25/23.75 µg), Ceftazidime (30 µg), Ceftazidime/Clavulanic Acid (30/10 µg), Ceftriaxone (30 µg) Ofloxacin (5 µg), Levofloxacin (5 µg), Imipenem (10 µg), Cefpodoxime (10 µg), Cefotaxime (30 µg), Cefepime (30 µg), Cefixime (5 µg), Cefoperazone (75 µg), Cefoperazone/Sulbactam (75/10 µg), Piperacillin/Tazobactam (100/10 µg), Fosfomycin (200 µg), Polymyxin B (300 Units) and Colistin (10 µg). All discs were obtained from Hi-Media Labs, Mumbai, India. *Escherichia coli* ATCC 25922 (non-ESBL producer) was used as a control strain.

Detection of ESBLs

Cefpodoxime (10 µg), Cefotaxime (30 µg), Ceftazidime (30 µg) and Ceftriaxone (30 µg) discs were used to screen for the ESBL production as per CLSI guidelines. The isolates which tested positive by the screening test were subjected to confirmatory test using Ceftazidime (30 µg) and Ceftazidime/clavulanic acid (30 µg/10 µg) discs. The results were interpreted according to the CLSI guidelines [9]. (Figure-1)

Figure 1: Disk Potentiation Test for ESBL Detection

Detection of Carbapenemases:

Imipenem (10 µg) discs were used to screen for the Carbapenemases production. The isolates which tested positive by the screening test were subjected to confirmatory test using Imipenem-EDTA

(10/750 µg) discs. Modified Hodge test was done for the confirmation of Carbapenem resistant Enterobacteriaceae.[10]

The results were interpreted according to the CLSI guidelines [9]. (Figure-2&3)

Figure 2: Imipenem-EDTA double-disk synergy test

Figure 3: Modified Hodge test for Carbapenemases

Detection of MDR: MDR Enterobacteriaceae (MDRE) are the organisms resistant to any three different classes of antibiotics as defined by the previous guidelines [11]. MDR isolates that are resistant to at least one agent in three or more clas-

ses of antimicrobials of the following groups- Cephalosporins, Fluoroquinolones, Aminoglycosides, Folate pathway inhibitors (trimethoprim-sulfamethoxazole) and Nitrofurantoin. (Figure-4)

Figure 4: MDR Enterobacteriaceae (MDRE)

Fosfomycin Minimum Inhibitory Concentration: MIC of Fosfomycin was tested by E-test strip (Hi-Media Laboratories, India) with Fosfomycin gradient concentrations ranging from 0.064 µg/mL to 1,024 µg/mL. The E strip was placed at the middle of contact with the agar

surface and incubation was done at 35°C for 16-18 hours.

Interpretation of E-test: <64 µg/mL is sensitive and >64 µg/mL is resistant. (Figure-5)

Figure 5: Fosfomycin Minimum Inhibitory Concentration by E Test

Results

Demographic Distribution: Age and sex-wise distribution of 200 samples was shown in the [Table-1/Fig-6]. Maximum number of cases (88%) was from adult populations (20-60 years). Out of 200 Urine samples, 79 were males and 121 were females.

Table 1: Age-wise distribution of Clinical samples

Age-group (years)	Number	Percentage (%)
Paediatric (0-12)	20	10%
Adolescent (13-19)	4	2%
Adult (20-60)	176	88%
Geriatric (>60)	0	0%
Total	200	100%

Figure 6: Sex Wise Distribution

Organism wise distribution of urinary isolates: A total of 200 urine samples were received fulfilling the inclusion criteria. Among these, 58 samples showed significant growth. Of these 58 patients with significant growth of organisms, 23

(39.65%) were males and 35 (60.35%) were females. There were 36 (60.67%) isolates of E. coli, 16 (18.82%) isolates of Klebsiella pneumoniae, 4 (4.21%) isolates of Pseudomonas

spp. and 2 (12.35%) isolates of *Proteus vulgaris*. (Figure-7)

Figure 7: Organism wise distribution of Clinical isolates

Resistance Pattern of Urinary isolates

Among the 36 isolates of *E. coli*, high rate of resistance was seen to Cephalosporins, Fluoroquinolones, and Aminoglycosides. All 36 (100%) were susceptible to Colistin, and 34 (94.44%) were susceptible to Fosfomycin. Among the 16 isolates of *K. pneumoniae*, the majority were resistant to Cephalosporins and Fluoroquinolones. All 16 (100%) were susceptible to Colistin and 14 (87.5%) isolates were susceptible to Fosfomycin. All 4 (100%) were resistant to Ceftazidime, Ciprofloxacin and Levofloxacin and none were resistant to Colistin. 2 isolates of *Proteus* spp. were susceptible to Colistin and Fosfomycin.

Fosfomycin sensitivity among resistant uropathogens

There were total 54 Enterobacteriaceae isolates of *E. coli*, *K. pneumoniae* and *Proteus mirabilis*. Among these 41 (75.93%) were ESBL producers, of which 31 were *E. coli* and 10 were *K. pneumoniae* and 13 (24.07%) were non ESBL producers, of which 5 were *E. coli*, 6 were *K. pneumoniae*, and 2 *P. mirabilis*. [Table 2]

Among 54 Enterobacteriaceae isolates, 20 (37.03%) were Carbapenem resistant Enterobacteriaceae and 19 (35.18%) isolates were found to be MDRE.

Among 54 Enterobacteriaceae isolates, tested for susceptibility, 50 (92.59%) out of 54 were found to be Fosfomycin susceptible, 89.47% of MDRE [Table 3] and 90% of CRE [Table 4] were found to be susceptible to Fosfomycin (MIC range for Fosfomycin was 0.25–512 µg/ml).

Table 2: Fosfomycin sensitivity among Extended Spectrum

Organism	ESBL producer (%)	Non-ESBL producer (%)
<i>E. coli</i>	29/31(93.54%)	5/5(100%)
<i>K. pneumoniae</i>	8/10(80%)	6/6(100%)
<i>P. mirabilis</i>	0	2/2(100%)
Total	37/41(90.24%)	13/13(100%)

Table 3: Fosfomycin sensitivity among Multidrug Resistant

Organism	MDRE (%)	Non-MDRE (%)
<i>E. coli</i>	11/12 (91.66)	23/24(95.83)
<i>K. pneumoniae</i>	6/7(85.71)	8/9(88.88%)
<i>P. mirabilis</i>	0	2/2(100%)
Total	17/19(89.47%)	33/35(94.28%)

Table 4: Fosfomycin sensitivity among Carbapenem-resistant Enterobacteriaceae

Organism	CRE (%)	Non-CRE (%)
<i>E. coli</i>	12/13(92.3%)	22/23 (95.65)
<i>K. pneumoniae</i>	6/7(85.71%)	8/9(88.88%)

P. mirabilis	0	2/2(100%)
Total	18/20(90%)	32/34(94.11%)

Discussion

Fosfomycin is a novel antibiotic with good in vitro activity against the common pathogens causing UTI, particularly toward the Enterobacteriaceae. Fosfomycin is active against both Gram-negative and Gram-positive pathogens, including Enterococcus spp., Staphylococcus aureus, E.coli, Salmonella spp., Shigella spp., Klebsiella, Enterobacter spp., Serratia spp., Citrobacter spp., and P. mirabilis [3].

The activity of Fosfomycin was evaluated as early as 1997 by Dastidar et al. Fosfomycin was found to possess somewhat lower activity against Staphylococcus aureus compared with other Penicillins; however, it showed powerful activity toward E. coli, Klebsiella spp., and P. mirabilis[12]. Of 54 isolates, majority were E. coli (60.67%) followed by Klebsiella (18.82%), which is in accordance with other studies[13,14]. In this study 39.48% were ESBL producers and 25.45% were Carbapenemase resistant isolates, majority of these isolates showed susceptibility to Fosfomycin 95.58%and 91.83% respectively. These findings are similar to other studies [15-19]. Fosfomycin was found to have a powerful activity against E. coli, Klebsiella and Proteus [12]. Marie et al has reported that Fosfomycin and Colistin were the two most effective antimicrobial agent against Multi-drug resistant uropathogens (MDR)[20]. In spite of this high rate of susceptibility, Fosfomycin is an undervalued agent for complicated Urinary tract infections (UTI) with MDR pathogens.

In this study,41 (75.93%) were ESBL producers. E.coli 34 (94.44%) were susceptible to Fosfomycin. Among the 36 isolates of E. coli, 34 (94.44%) were susceptible to Fosfomycin. Among the 16 isolates of K. pneumoniae, 14 (87.5%) isolates were susceptible to Fosfomycin. In a study done by Gupta et al. from Chandigarh, among 150 uropathogenic strains of E. coli, 52.6% of isolates were ESBL producers, and all strains were susceptible to Fosfomycin [14]. In another study by Mittal et al., it was found that Fosfomycin was 100% sensitive to uropathogenic E. coli strains [16]. In this present study, 92.59% isolates were susceptible to Fosfomycin which is similar to the findings of a study done by Sabharwal and Sharma where it was found that 94.4% of the isolates causing UTI were susceptible to Fosfomycin [17]. In a study done by Rajenderan et al., it was found that Fosfomycin was the only antibiotic that effectively inhibited 90% of the strains of E. coli and Klebsiella spp [18].

In the current study, among 54 Enterobacteriaceae isolates,20 (37.03%) were Carbapenem resistant Enterobacteriaceae. The susceptibility to

Fosfomycin was also found to be quite high, at 90%, which is really encouraging in the grim scenario of more commonly prescribed nephrotoxic polymyxins as the salvage therapy for these cases. The Present study revealed about 19 (35.18%) isolates was found to be MDRE. Out of the total of 19 MDRE isolates, which were resistant to at least three (or more) groups of antibiotics, 17 (89.47%) were susceptible to Fosfomycin. Published literature suggested that Fosfomycin might be an effective antibiotic against ESBL-producing, CR, and MDR strains of E. coli [15,21]. Despite of these reports of high percentage of in vitro susceptibility of Fosfomycin, antibiotic susceptibility profile varies not only from time to time but also from one geographical place to another. It is also an underrated agent for complicated UTI cases though urinary concentration. Determination of MIC to Fosfomycin is necessary for the detection of resistance. Therefore, judicious use of Fosfomycin in clinical practice is warranted to avoid increased rate of Fosfomycin resistance among ESBL-producing, CR, and MDR strains.

Conclusion:

Fosfomycin is the most active antimicrobial agent against common uropathogens including ESBL producers and Carbapenem-resistant Enterobacteriaceae in this era of antimicrobial resistance. In spite of this high rate of susceptibility, Fosfomycin is an undervalued agent for complicated Urinary tract infections (UTI) with MDR pathogens. It can be recommended as a promising and safe alternative oral agent for both outpatient and inpatient therapy of UTIs, particularly in countries, where its prescription habits among clinicians is scarce. However, further studies are needed to evaluate the various in vitro phenotypic and genotypic profiles of Fosfomycin resistance among uropathogens.

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